

Emissive Brightening in Molecular Graphene Nanoribbons by Twilight States

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Abstract

Carbon nanomaterials are expected to be bright and efficient emitters, but structural polydispersity, intermolecular interactions and the intrinsic presence of dark states suppress their photoluminescence. Here, we overcome all of these limitations in synthetically-made graphene nanoribbons, demonstrating extremely bright photoluminescence in applicable conditions such as solutions and solid films. We identify hitherto-unrecognised twilight states, where intervalley mixing brightens up the conventionally-dark states. The resulting high spectral resolution reveals strong vibron-electron coupling, and how phonon modes unexpectedly affect

30 **absorption and emission differently, due to the simultane-**
31 **ous presence of Herzberg–Teller and Franck–Condon cou-**
32 **plings. These results open the path to the tailored chem-**
33 **ical design of nanocarbon optical devices, via gap tuning**
34 **and side-chain functionalisation, and to the optical investiga-**
35 **tion and manipulation of topological states in graphenoids.**

36 **Keywords:** graphene nanoribbons, photoluminescence, graphene, twilight
37 states, dark states, electron-phonon coupling

38 Main

39 Introduction

40 Most semiconducting carbon nano-structures have direct band gaps and
41 extreme quantum confinement, so they would be expected to yield superb pho-
42 toluminescence (PL) quantum efficiencies (PLQEs) from their excitons which
43 have large binding energies [1–3]. Alas, non-radiative dark states, disorder,
44 and interactions among the carbon nano-structures all lead to substantial PL
45 quenching [4–7], limiting their potential for applications in bio-imaging, solar
46 energy conversion, in opto-electronics and in display devices, as well as in
47 quantum technologies for single-photon sources, up-conversion, and sensing
48 [2, 3, 8, 9]. The most appealing systems, those with large exciton-diffusion
49 coherent lengths, such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), are actually those most
50 affected. CNTs need de-bundling, but covalent functionalisation breaks the
51 π -conjugation, and non-covalent surfactants are randomly arranged around
52 the CNT surface, so both mechanisms introduce disorder and severely disrupt
53 electronic properties, limiting the PLQE [7, 10, 11].

54 Moreover, the presence of degenerate valley states introduces a fundamental
55 limitation by producing dark excitons in CNTs and graphene. Dark excitons
56 occur in carbon nanomaterials because momentum conservation allows PL only
57 from states that have zero net angular momentum. In semiconducting CNTs,
58 the multiple K-points of the graphene Brillouin zone lead to the formation
59 of a dark valley doublet state and two coupled singlets, only one of which is
60 bright (Fig. 1a). Graphene nanoribbons (GNRs) with zigzag edges are largely
61 equivalent to armchair CNTs: their edges generate a bandgap with the typical
62 bright and dark states [12, 13].

63 Edge engineering and twilight states in cove-GNR

64 Here we show, when the edge structure of the molecular GNR is engineered
65 so as to introduce a periodic modulation of the edge states as in cove-edged
66 GNRs (Fig. 1a), dramatic changes occur. With a threefold edge symmetry,
67 zone-folding of the dark states into the Γ -point zone centre allows all of the
68 previously-dark excitons to mix and become much more emissive (Fig. 1a),

69 increasing the theoretical limit of the PLQE fourfold. To distinguish them
 70 from conventional bright states, we dub these new long-lived emissive states
 that arise from previously-dark ones as "twilight states". The projection of

Fig. 1 Bright, Dark and Twilight States. (a) Comparison of graphene, a (6,6) carbon nanotube, a zigzag GNR and a cove-edge GNR, showing the real and reciprocal lattices, with K , K' , M , Γ and X points indicated, together with the discretization produced by lateral confinement (green lines). The bands of each nanostructure are coloured based on their projection ζ of each point onto the graphene state along the rightmost green k line that passes through $K - M - K'$, resulting in bright and dark states, from the linear combinations of valleys, or yielding the brighter twilight states for cove-edge GNRs. (b) Zoom-in of the projected density of states (PDOS) and band structure of a synthetically-achievable cove-edge GNR, including the contributions from the backbone and the side groups as per Fig. 2a. Transitions are labelled by their main inter-band contribution.

71 the wave-function of several different carbon nanostructures $\Psi_{n,k}$ onto the
 72 graphene wave-function $\Psi_{n,k}^{gra}$, called $\zeta = \|\langle \Psi_{n,k}^{gra} | \Psi_{n,k} \rangle\|$ offers a quantitative
 73 insight into the nature of these new states. A plot of ζ for each wave-vector k
 74 and band n shows that armchair CNT and zigzag GNR states project almost
 75 perfectly onto the original graphene ones, and thus form the usual bright and
 76 dark excitons, while valleys become very strongly mixed in cove-edged GNRs
 77 (Fig. 1a). Now, not all states can be projected onto combinations of graphene
 78 ones, and $k = 0$ relaxation to the ground state by photon emission is always
 79 allowed (Fig. 1a). The projected density of states for chemically-feasible GNRs
 80 shows a low-energy spectrum dominated by the GNR backbone (Fig. 1b).
 81 The absorption no longer belongs to well-defined interband transitions, but
 82 to groups of closely-lying transitions near the Γ point[14]. In particular, the
 83 energies of $c_1 \leftarrow v_2$, $c_2 \leftarrow v_1$ electronic transitions are close, and can only be
 84 labelled by their dominant contribution[14].
 85

Enhanced solubility via *N-n*-octadecylmaleimide side groups

Even so, GNRs remain plagued by the other issues that affect CNTs, and, to date, spectra of GNRs in solution have remained broad and featureless, an indication of inter-ribbon exciton transfer[15, 16]. Finer spectral features are available only in conditions incompatible with applications, such as single ribbons produced by surface synthesis under high-vacuum[13].

We overcome these issues by using cove-edged GNRs functionalised with bulky groups, here cycloadducts from the Diels–Alder reaction of anthracene with *N-n*-octadecylmaleimide. These are covalently attached to the edges with a grafting ratio of 77% [17] (Fig.2a) and spaced regularly at the GNR edges, thus minimizing disorder in the resulting de-bundled GNRs [18]. The bulky groups are ≈ 0.5 nm, larger than the inter-layer spacing of graphite, and thus efficiently suppress π - π -stacking interactions among GNRs. The resulting samples are remarkable: they display exceptional solubility in organic solvents, such as toluene, tetrahydrofuran, and chloroform, remain stable for at least 16 months without precipitation, and thin film samples with identical optical behaviour can be produced by inclusion inside transparent polymer matrices, see materials and methods. The improvements in the optical response are striking: the PL emission is exceptionally bright, with well-defined features (Fig.2d). By contrast, in non-debundled samples of cove-edged GNRs functionalised with the usual dodecyl groups (fig. S1), which are much less effective at separating the GNRs, we only see broad and featureless photoluminescence (PL) peaks, similar to previous literature[15] (fig. S2) with around 3 orders of magnitude lower peak intensities (Fig.2b).

Phonon modes revealed by Raman scattering

Raman scattering reveals the phonon modes of the new debundled cove-edged GNRs. The radial-breathing-like-mode (RBLM) (31.6 meV) becomes the dominant Raman feature, with a weaker overtone at twice the energy and two weaker peaks at 15 and 20 meV, likely associated with out-of-plane and longitudinal acoustic modes[19, 20], also visible (Fig.2c). A lateral zone-folding model, insensitive to the edge structure[20, 21], yields a RBLM energy

$$E_{RBLM} = \hbar\omega_R = \frac{399.5 \text{ \AA meV}}{w_{GNR}} = 32 \text{ meV},$$

which matches observations. Local density approximation calculations provide the vibrational symmetries and reproduce quantitatively the vibrational response, with the calculated RBLM energy, 32.2 meV, matching the main Raman peak (Fig.2c). It is important to note that the symmetry of the RBLM produces a modulation of the GNR width, with large displacements at the edges, and is thus likely to couple strongly to electronic modes. The higher energy D (166 meV) and G (200 meV) Raman modes[22] are as expected, but their higher order modes are hidden by the extremely bright PL and only emerge at low- T due to the narrowing PL emission. By contrast, the higher-order D and G modes can be easily seen in the bundled GNRs above the very weak PL (fig. S3).

Fig. 2 Photoluminescence enhancement and spectroscopic features (a) Structure of the molecular GNRs. The GNR backbone is highlighted in yellow-green and the de-bundling side groups in gray. (b) Comparison of the photoluminescence peak intensities for bundled and de-bundled samples, acquired in the same conditions. (c) Raman spectrum on thin films at 2.33 eV excitation. The G, D, radial-breathing-like mode (RBLM) and its overtone are labelled, together with calculated atomic displacements, including anthracene side groups for the RBLM, and only the backbone for the overtone. (d) Photoluminescence and absorption spectra of GNR thin films at 77 K (dots), and modelling (black lines). The individual contributions are shown for the main excitations (red), RBLM (green), G (yellow) and D (violet) modes.

129 Low temperature PL and electron-phonon coupling

130 The excellent resolution of the optical response obtained allows a complete
 131 unravelling of the mechanisms at play and indeed reveals the fundamental
 132 importance of the interplay of electronic and vibrational states. The absorp-
 133 tion spectrum of the GNRs consists of three wide peaks at 2.29 eV, 2.49 eV and
 134 2.63 eV plus a narrow feature at 2.09 eV (Fig.2d). The overall PLQE for the
 135 de-bundled GNRs reaches a value of $6.4 \pm 0.2\%$ at room temperature (Table
 136 S1), with a gradual enhancement of the emission on lowering the tempera-
 137 ture T (Fig.3e), so that the total PL intensity increases by 20%, leading to a
 138 remarkably high overall $8 \pm 0.5\%$ PLQE already beyond the theoretical limit of
 139 6% for CNTs and conventional GNRs [12].

Fig. 3 Temperature dependence. **a)** PL spectra acquired on thin films at different T (colour bar), with photoexcitation at 2.33 eV. **b)** Debye–Waller factor α as a function of T for photoexcitation at 2.33 and 3.06 eV (green and violet, respectively). Lines are linear regressions. **c)** Zero-phonon-line position vs T for photoexcitation at 2.33 and 3.06 eV (green and violet). Lines are fitted with the Fan equation. **d)** Temperature evolution of the zero-phonon peak FWHM under 2.33 eV excitation shown with line fit (see text). **e)** T -dependence of the PL peak intensity under 3.06 eV excitation, shown with a two 1D exciton fit (see text).

140 The 2.09 eV feature is present in both absorption and emission at the same
 141 energy, becomes more visible upon lowering T (Fig.3a), and is thus the zero-
 142 phonon line (ZPL) of the inter-band transition. This observation is exceptional
 143 for carbon nanostructures, where the ZPL is usually broadened by polydisper-
 144 sity and inter-structure energy transfers, and demonstrates the superb
 145 level of cleanliness of the optical response in de-bundled GNRs. We can thus
 146 probe directly the T -evolution of the semiconducting bandgap (Δ_G) from the
 147 ZPL position (PL for 3.06 eV excitation, fig. S4). The low- T non-monotonic
 148 behaviour (Fig.3c) resembles that observed in semiconducting CNTs [23], with
 149 the slight decrease in the 2.33 eV data probably due to increasing emission
 150 from the 'twilight states' at slightly lower energy. It is important to notice
 151 that, as in other carbon-based nanomaterials [23], the total shift is around 10
 152 meV, much larger than the 1 meV effect produced by thermal expansion. The
 153 behaviour shows good agreement with what is expected for semiconductors,
 154 where [24] $\Delta_G(T) = \Delta_G(0) + A(1 - e^{E_{\text{ph}}/k_{\text{B}}T})^{-1}$, where k_{B} is the Boltzmann
 155 constant, A is the Fan parameter, and the Bose-Einstein statistical factor con-
 156 tains the characteristic phonon energy E_{ph} [25]. We obtain $E_{\text{ph}} = 30 \pm 2$ meV
 157 and 35 ± 2 meV for the two excitation wavelengths, close to the RBLM energy,
 158 revealing that phonon coupling to the RBLM is the key mechanism modul-
 159 ating Δ_G , as also backed up by the T -dependence of the D and G Raman lines
 160 (fig. S5). Intuitively, this is expected: the RBLM is the one altering the GNR
 161 width, responsible for the electronic confinement.

The T -dependence of the line-broadening parameter $\Gamma(T)$ of the ZPL reveals what phonons play a major role. Fitting with the expression $\Gamma(T) = \Gamma_0 + \Gamma_{\text{ph}} = \Gamma_0 + \gamma (e^{E_{\text{ph}}/k_{\text{B}}T} - 1)^{-1}$, yields the inhomogeneous broadening linked to scattering on terminations[26], $\Gamma_0 = 16.89 \pm 0.03$ meV, the homogeneous broadening produced by phonon scattering[27] Γ_{ph} , and an electron-phonon coupling strength $\gamma = 2.1 \pm 0.3$ meV with phonons at energy $E_{\text{ph}} = 7.1 \pm 0.7$ meV. Interestingly, these are the very same transverse bending modes that strongly modulate the electron transport in transistors made from the same GNRs[17].

A similar energy is obtained for the gap between bright and twilight states, Δ , as extracted from the ZPL peak intensity vs T (Fig.3e). Assuming exciton thermalisation, the PL intensity I can be described as [5] $I \propto \frac{1}{(T^2 + T_0^2)^{1/4}} \cdot \frac{m + e^{-\Delta/kT}}{1 + e^{-\Delta/kT}}$ where the power-law dependence is characteristic of one-dimensional excitons, m describes the spectral weight of the excitonic states[4] and T_0 is a T -independent Lorentzian broadening term. The intensity maximum around 75K indicates the presence of two sets of excitonic states separated by $\Delta = 6$ meV, similarly to CNTs[5, 28], but with the spectral weight of twilight states $m = 0.68 \pm 0.04 \approx 4$ times larger[5] than that of the CNT dark states (Fig.3e). This means that, while multiple excitonic states are present, they do not quench PL nearly as much as in CNTs.

The resulting emission is thus so bright that it reveals a plethora of different spectral features (Fig.2d). All features of the optical response are reproduced using a Franck–Condon-like model that includes G and RBLM phonons (supplementary Text S1, Table S2 and fig. S6) plus a low-energy excimer peak at 1850 meV (identified from bundled 4-CGNRs) and a wide Gaussian contribution for the high-energy absorbance (fig. S6). The maxima of both PL and absorbance are separated by one G-band phonon from the ZPL and the periodicity of the PL features matches the predicted RBLM phonons. The 0-1 vibronic transition is dominant and exceeds the amplitude allowed by purely Frank-Condon behaviour only below 150 K. The spectra were analysed by considering the Debye–Waller factor $\alpha = \frac{J}{J + \Phi}$, which determines the probability of zero-phonon transitions [29] by comparing the integrated intensities of the ZPL $J(\omega)$ and of the phonon wing $\Phi(\omega)$. The type of electron-phonon coupling present is then revealed by the T -dependence of α (Fig.3b). In purely Franck–Condon (FC) coupled systems, α is strongly T -dependent, while for Herzberg–Teller (HT) coupling α is T -independent [30]. In the presence of both FC and HT couplings, we expect α to be different for absorption and PL bands [31]. Our measurements at 77 K give $\alpha = 0.010 \pm 0.003$ for absorbance vs. $\alpha = 0.06 \pm 0.01$ for PL, showing that both types of coupling are actually present, in agreement with theoretical predictions of GNRs with edge modulations (Fig. 1a) [14].

This analysis allows us to build a full energy level diagram, where the twilight states are separated from the usual bright ones, and a series of different vibronically coupled modes produce strong mixing with the electronic states and enhance the PLQE (Fig. 2d,4a).

PLE and time-resolved PL spectroscopy

Photoluminescence excitation (PLE) spectra complete the understanding of the fundamental vibronic electron-phonon interaction for twilight states (Fig.4b). The three absorbance peaks observed confirm the assignment, but

Fig. 4 Electron-vibron mixing and temporal evolution. (a) Energy diagram for the GNR transitions, with G modes in yellow, RBLMs in green (G and RBLM mixing is schematically depicted) and the twilight states in violet. (b) PLE map of GNRs in chloroform solution, excited with a white light source (left) and its normalisation by peak intensity along the excitation energy axis (right). (c) Position of the $E_{21} + G$ peak for different emission energies, with the ZPL position (red) and the energy spacing of the RBLM (green). (d) Time evolution of the normalised PL spectra, acquired with 3.06 eV excitation in solution. (e) Temporal evolution of GNR modes. (f) Logarithmic plot of the 1G and ZPL intensities (yellow and orange, respectively) vs time, and fits to bi-exponentials (lines).

normalising the PLE spectra for the peak intensity shows abrupt variations of the brightest excitation: upon crossing the ZPL, the peak excitation energy shifts from $E_{\text{exc}} = 2.30$ eV (ZPL+1G) to 2.34 eV (ZPL+1G+1RBLM) (Fig.4c). This observation unveils the mechanism producing emission: below the ZPL, creation of one G phonon is the dominant mechanism in both absorption and consecutive PL emission, whereas emission of an RBLM plus a G phonon dominates the absorption for ZPL emission. Close to the ZPL, the very strong mixing of the G and RBLM modes also yields $E_{21} + G$ peak oscillations with an energy corresponding to the RBLM. The mechanism is not universal and is different for the second interband transition at $E_{\text{exc}} = 2.60$ eV, which is much stronger in the PLE compared to the absorbance data (fig. S7). Carriers excited into the second conduction band are more likely to relax internally from the second to the first conduction band at low k values than to follow a multi-phonon-assisted transition.

Finally, we reveal how the twilight states respond dynamically: PL spectra show emission from vibronic coupling to the RBLM and G modes at first, while by 10 ns emission is dominated by the long lived, higher energy D and ZPL transitions directly to the ground state (Fig.4d,e). This indicates that an initial, very bright, cascade from the bright states is followed after a few ns by

the new strong emission process from the twilight states, in a timescale compatible with state mixing mediated by vibronic coupling. The state lifetimes can be extracted from bi-exponential fitting of the time-dependence of the signal (Fig.4f), yielding 0.6 ± 0.1 ns for the bright states, and 3.6 ± 0.3 ns and 2.9 ± 0.3 ns for the ZPL and D-mode emission from the twilight ones (Fig.4a).

Conclusions

These results reveal GNRs as the carbon nanostructures that can overcome excitonic K-K' valley quenching to enable bright optical emission. The 8% quantum yields achieved in these first experiments here are already beyond those of most nanocarbon materials[7, 32–34]. More importantly, we reveal new mechanisms that can be used to turn dark states into much brighter twilight ones, where the fundamental symmetry is altered by the perfect edge modulation obtained by molecular design. These newly observed twilight states not only yield high PL efficiencies, but also a superior resolution of the spectral features, so that access to the fundamental optical processes is available. Based on this, optics can now be used to investigate topological and quantum coherent processes[35, 36] in carbon nanostructures. Direct insight into the mechanisms, with internal relaxation processes dominated by phonons, already indicates long exciton lifetimes and associated exciton motion, offering a way to chemically tune the optical response. The chemical versatility of GNRs also opens up their use as a new family that can be integrated with established systems such as poly-acenes[37]. It is notable that the level of detail, unprecedented in extended carbon nanostructures, is achieved both in solutions and thin films, i.e. in conditions suitable for applications. The GNR side-groups can be modified to bind to biological structures, or bear quantum coherent units, making these systems an exceptionally versatile optical platform for bio-imaging,[3] optoelectronics[17, 35, 36] and quantum technologies[38, 39].

Methods

Raman. Raman spectra were acquired with a Jobin Yvon T64000 triple spectrometer and an Andor DU420A-OE CCD and excited with a Ventus solo Nd:YAG laser with excitation energy $E_{exc} = 2.33$ eV. **Absorption, photoluminescence and PLE** of GNRs were investigated in chloroform solutions (0.2 and 0.05 mg/ml, respectively) for $T = 295$ K and in transparent EVA polymer matrices at lower T . Absorbance measurements were conducted with a Perkin-Elmer UV/Vis-NIR spectrophotometer Lambda 35. PL data were acquired with a Princeton Applied Research Model 1235 triple grating 0.3m spectrograph coupled to an Andor iDus 416 CCD and excited with a LaserQuantum Ventus532 532nm (2.33 eV) laser or a 405nm (3.06 eV) laser diode. PLE maps were measured with a 75W Xenon lamp (Photon Technology International Inc.) scanned by a monochromator and connected to a spectrometer leading to an InGaS photodiode array (OMA V, Princeton Instruments). Note that the Xenon lamp does not have sufficient power to operate at resolutions required to

272 resolve the ZPL. **Time-resolved PL** was measured on a PicoQuant FluoTime
273 300 (4 ps resolution) and a PicoQuant LHD-P-C-405 (3.06 eV) pulsed laser
274 diode at 4 MHz repetition rate on GNR in chloroform solution (0.05 mg/ml).
275 **PLQE**. Photoluminescence quantum efficiency was measured with a Roithner
276 MLL-III-405-200mW (3.06 eV) laser, an integrating sphere and a and a
277 calibrated QEPro OceanInsight grating spectrometer.

278 **First principle calculations.** Density Functional Theory (DFT) calcula-
279 tions were implemented in SIESTA[40]. We employed Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof
280 (PBE) generalized gradient approximation (GGA) functional[41] in the band
281 structure calculation. Energy cut-off of 400 Ry and the Monkhorst-Pack grid
282 of (21,1,1) were used. A vacuum region of at least 18 Å is added in nonperiodic
283 directions to prevent unwanted interactions. We removed the alkyl chain in the
284 side groups to simplify the calculation. The structure was optimized until the
285 maximum force on the atoms is less than 0.01 eV/Å. In the Density of States
286 (DOS) calculation gaussian broadening of 0.05 eV is used for all bands.

287 In the phonon calculation, we adopted tighter criteria for structure relax-
288 ation and convergence. Perdew-Zunger (PZ) local density approximation
289 (LDA) functional[42] was used. The energy cut-off was increased to 800 Ry.
290 Monkhorst-Pack k-sampling was set to (50,1,1). Due to the computational
291 complexity, we further simplify the result and only keep anthracene in the side
292 groups. The structure was relaxed with maximum allowed force of 0.004 eV/
293 Å. Then a supercell of [3,1,1] was created for calculating phonon dispersion.

294 **Declarations**

295 **General.** The authors declare no competing financial interests. Supplemen-
296 tary information accompanies this paper.

297 **Author Contributions.** BS performed the optical measurements. FK
298 performed the numerical calculations. XY and WN prepared the samples
299 supervised by JM, LB and XF. RN and LB conceived the experiments. BS,
300 FK, RN and LB analysed the data, developed the interpretative framework
301 and prepared the manuscript. LB made the figures. All authors discussed the
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